

3D Printing of Assistive Device for Motorized Wheelchair

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Abstract— Increasingly users of assistive devices have had difficulties to adapt and even to make use of this technology, generating many cases of abandonment of these devices. In general, this may happen due to the user's lack of identification with the product, since each patient has specific needs, and the device may not meet them. This article has the proposal of creating completely customized assistive devices, so that it is possible to meet all the demands and limitations of its user, besides guaranteeing the use of the tool. Because of this, we made a prototype of an assistive device to be attached to a joystick of a motorized wheelchair, so that the amputee volunteer could get around more easily, creating a better fit between the amputee hand and the joystick. For this, the whole project was made with the active participation of the person involved, besides the proposal that the piece be totally printed in a 3D printer.

Keywords — 3D Printing, Assistive Technology, Personalized Technology, Assistive Device.

I. Introduction

Assistive technologies are more and more present in the lives of people with disabilities, being used to improve their quality of life, bringing more independence and autonomy in their day-to-day activities. These devices have the role of enabling the individual to perform tasks, helping, for instance, in the reduced motor function, such as canes, motorized wheelchairs and even orthoses [1]. Despite having an important role in the adaptation of people with special needs, they don't always have the ideal conditions for their user, some assistive devices end up being discarded by the user for not providing comfort, usability and functionality, requiring optimization [2] [3].

There are some causes for this user dissatisfaction with the device, one of them being incompatibility [2]. One of the challenges in the creation of this type of tool is the lack of customization, which is an important point for the identification of the patient with the product. Since each of them has individual needs, a more generic device may not bring the necessary assistance, failing to meet the real needs of those who are using it and becoming inappropriate.[4]

A promising solution to this problem is the use of 3D printer to develop these devices in a dynamic where the user and the designer work together, being possible that all details and preferences are discussed and adjusted [4][6]. Through it,

it is possible to create completely customized and tailored devices, with direct participation of the user in all the development, precisely attending the existing difficulties. Moreover, 3D printing allows a low cost and even more agility in the manufacturing process, delivering high cost-effectiveness.[5]

This paper aims to present a prototype of an assistive tool built in the 3D printer for a motorized wheelchair with active participation of the volunteer. Furthermore, to score the benefits and facilities of this method. The expectation is that this methodology can be applied in other cases, preserving the preferences of each user.

II. Materials and Methods

In order to make the volunteer participate in the whole prototype development process, a meeting was held with him to define all the specifications and details of the device. In this meeting, it was possible for all the user's needs to be exposed and to determine what characteristics he would like the device to have. After all the points were set, a 3D scan (full scale) of the individual's arm was made, as well as the part of the wheelchair that would undergo the modifications.

To scan the amputated limb and the chair controls, an iPad Air 2 was used, which, together with another device called the Struct Sensor, made it possible to scan using accessible devices. The sensor used has an app of the same name, which has this feature for scanning and developing a 3D model with good accuracy of measurements and details.

Using the technologies, the volunteer was asked to stand in certain positions so that it would be possible to capture the limb's data more accurately and obtain a more precise 3D model developed from the scan. The arm was asked to be bent at an angle of approximately 90°, in addition to the arm being stretched out, so that the modeling could be done. The same happened with the chair, where we asked the patient to stand in a position that would allow the chair to be scanned. One of the biggest challenges was the need for the patient to remain as still as possible so that the data could be captured correctly without any shaking or defects in the rendering of the 3D model.

Fig. 1 – The Wheelchair arm 3D Scanning, made using an Ipad Air 2 the Struct Sensor and the app Struct Sensor

The Fig. 1 shows the 3D model of the Wheelchair controls, that have been used as a base model to have the dimensions, orientation and movement to build the prototype.

Fig. 2 – The Patient Arm (bent arm) 3D Scanning, made using an Ipad Air 2 the Struct Sensor and the app Struct Sensor

Fig. 3 - The Patient Arm (extended arm) 3D Scanning, made using an Ipad Air 2 the Struct Sensor and the app Struct Sensor.

The Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 were used to have the shape and dimensions of patient arm in order to make a comfortable, adaptable and user-friendly prototype, that can solve the main problem of the difficult of wheelchair control allied to comfort and efficiency.

After the scanning, using a measuring tape, measurements were taken for that the equipment created would fit precisely. All dimensions found can be seen in figures 4 and 5.

Fig. 4 - 3D scanning voluntary arm (measures).

Fig. 5 - 3D scanning wheelchair arm (measures).

Based on the data obtained using the Fusion 360 software, an initial prototype model was developed. This part will be attached to the chair joystick, where will improve the arm support, making it easier to control, since the user does not have his hands. To make a really good solution, we based on the patient's needs to create an user-centered technology, using this kind of methodology increase the effectiveness and increase the chance of the patient keeping using it.

III. Results and Discussion

The device was designed with a support and a coupling rod. The base consists of a rounded trapezoid, a shape that ensures that the amputated arm fits perfectly, as well as a front face that has a very thin base, in order to facilitate the entry of the individual's arm into the device. The coupling part consists of how this tool will be coupled to the wheelchair's joystick. With this in mind, we modelled a kind of hook, which can be adjusted with screws through another hook independent of the base of the support, in order to attach the object to the chair in a stable way. Figure 6 shows the model in a side view, Figure 7 in a top view and Figure 8 in a rear view.

Fig. 6 - Assistive Device (Fusion 360 modeling).

Fig. 7 - Assistive Device (Fusion 360 modeling).

Fig. 8 - Assistive Device (Fusion 360 modeling).

Fig. 9 - Independent hook (Fusion 360 modeling).

After developing the part, will be used to print it the material known as PLA (poly lactic acid), which is a polymer made up of lactic acid molecules. This material was chosen because it has rigid properties, is easy to mold and is affordable. This filament-shaped material will be placed in a 3D printer, model Ender 3 V2, to print.

Although the modeling turned out as expected, in terms of measurements and design, it was observed that there are points that could be improved, such as the issue of comfort. The rigid PLA-type material, when alone, may not provide the necessary comfort that a material in direct contact with the skin requires. With this in mind, the alternative would be

to combine the PLA structure coated with another material, such as silicone [5].

IV. Conclusions

This work is still in development, and it is necessary to finish the 3D printing tests and collect the evaluation of the volunteer regarding usability, comfort and if the product meets their demands. The device is expected to please the user and provide a higher quality of life. Future expectations are that more devices can be built based on the active participation model, ensuring that these technologies can be increasingly used.

References

- [1] RECENT trends in assistive technology for mobility. *Journal of NeuroEngineering and Rehabilitation*, [S. l.], 2012
- [2] DISPOSITIVOS de tecnologia assistiva: fatores relacionados ao abandono. *Cadernos de Terapia Ocupacional da UFSCar*, [S. l.], p. 611-624, 2015.
- [3] OPTIMIZATION of power wheelchair control for patients with severe Duchenne muscular dystrophy. Elsevier, [s. l.], 5 maio 2004. Disponível em: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0960896604000392>. Acesso em: 7 set. 2023.
- [4] DESIGN for assistive technology oriented to design methodology: a systematic review on user-centered design and 3D printing approaches. *Journal of the Brazilian Society of Mechanical Sciences and Engineering*, [S. l.], p. 483, 2021. Disponível em: <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s40430-021-03184-1>. Acesso em: 15 mar. 2023
- [5] HOW 3D printing technologies can contribute into an iterative design process? Case study to hit a drum for Disabled Children. *Production*, [S. l.], 201
- [6] CUSTOMIZED Power Wheelchair Joysticks Made by Three-Dimensional Printing Technology: A Pilot Study on the Environmental Adaptation Effects for Severe Quadriplegia. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, [s. l.], 13 jul. 2021. Disponível em: <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/18/14/7464>. Acesso em: 7 set. 2023.

